

High Frequency Dielectric Measurements and Destructive Testing for the Investigation of Water Uptake in Adhesively Bonded Joints

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SUMMARY: High frequency dielectric measurements on adhesively bonded joints, exposed to water at elevated temperatures are presented. Changes in dielectric loss and permittivity, measured in frequency and time domain, monitor the water ingress. These non-destructive data are then correlated to joint strength by performing destructive mechanical Mode I and Mode II analysis. Thermostatic, ageing environments at 50 °C and 65 °C were studied, along with a 50-65 °C thermal stepping cycle. Dielectric loss and permittivity increased with ageing and increased temperature. Thermal stepping produced results tending to thermostatic 50 °C ageing. After 238 days immersed at 65 °C, mechanical strengths were reduced to ~30 %, with visual adhesive failure around exposed edges. Correlation between destructive and non-destructive techniques details the sensitivity of high frequency dielectric methods, to moisture uptake. With the test programme completed, the potential of dielectric analysis to identify structural integrity of adhesively bonded joints will have been illustrated.

KEYWORDS: high frequency dielectrics, adhesively bonded joints, water uptake, non-destructive testing, epoxy, aluminium, carbon fibre.

INTRODUCTION

With the development of aluminium surface treatments [1,2,3] and advent of advanced composite materials, adhesive bonding, especially in the aerospace industry, is becoming ever more advantageous. Applications include the Nimrod, one of the first adhesively bonded aircraft, and the Eurofighter 2000 Typhoon, designed with 40 % of its structural mass fabricated from carbon fibre reinforced composites (CFRP) [4]. Advantages for using adhesively bonded joints are vast; ranging from increased strength and stiffness along with uniform stress distribution to improved aerodynamics and the ability to join materials of different thickness [5,6,7].

During service, exposure of such structural joints, whether aluminium or CFRP, to harsh environmental conditions are commonly experienced. Hot/moist climates are particularly detrimental to adhesive systems, requiring non-destructive evaluation to assess moisture content and to confirm structural integrity of the bonded joint. Current non-destructive techniques [8,9] include ultrasonic, thermography, radiography, acoustic, eddy currents and the Fokker bond test, but these cannot determine moisture content. Fortunately, as water is a

very polar molecule, dielectric measurement techniques may be implemented to monitor water absorption [10]. This type of evaluation has been proven to be highly sensitive [11] due to the high permittivity of water ($\epsilon' \approx 80$), thus warranting further developmental investigation.

HIGH FREQUENCY DIELECTRICS

The use of high frequency network analysers operating at frequencies ranging from 300 kHz to 3 GHz has allowed for the dielectric properties of adhesives and water absorption to be investigated. Data are collected using transmission line measurements in the frequency domain and can be transformed by Fourier inversion to be displayed as time domain. These methods calculate dielectric loss and permittivity along with the potential to evaluate the structural integrity of the joint, with respect to voids, disbonds and other interfacial defects caused by water ingress.

In the frequency domain, a sine wave voltage of fixed frequency is applied to one end of the specimen. The reflected signal is detected by the analyser, which computes the amplitude and phase relationship for transmitted and reflected waves. The permittivity is calculated by recording the voltage reflection coefficient, ρ_i , which is given by Eqn 1:

$$\rho_i = \frac{(Z_i - Z_o)}{(Z_i + Z_o)} \quad (1)$$

where Z_i and Z_o are the input impedance of the structure and the measurement system respectively.

When time domain measurements are displayed, the transit time for the wave to travel down the joint and be returned may be taken between the largest negative pulse and the first positive peak. The transit time, t , and permittivity, ϵ' , are related by:

$$\sqrt{\epsilon'} = \frac{C}{(2L/t)} \quad (2)$$

where C is the velocity of light and L , the length of the joint, resulting in a linear relationship.

EXPERIMENTAL

Two types of adhesively bonded joints were manufactured, aluminium bonded to aluminium and CFRP to CFRP, however only the aluminium results will be presented in this paper. The aluminium was series 2000 MTL Spec. L166 alloy (Cu, Mg and Si) which was pre-treated by British Aerospace, Prestwick, UK. Surface treating the aluminium consisted of a degrease, alkaline clean, chromic/sulfuric acid pickle, chromic acid anodise and a corrosion resistant primer. This process produces an oxide film [2] of approximately 400 nm, greatly increasing adhesion capability. Fibredux 914 carbon fibre reinforced plastic, 914C-TS(6K)-5.34%, prepreg from Hexcel, Duxford, UK was used, laid up in eleven unidirectional layers, to achieve similar bending characteristics to the aluminium. Both the aluminium and CFRP systems were bonded using Scotch-Weld Brand AF 163-2M, manufactured by 3M, UK. This is a thermosetting modified epoxy structural adhesive, supplied on a non-woven supporting material, in film form. The adhesive was autoclave cured (125 °C and 2 bar for 1 hour) using 0.2 mm Teflon as a spacer to ensure a uniform bond thickness.

Before ageing, each joint was dielectrically analysed and the data stored, later used as reference measurements. Ageing was conducted on samples submerged under water at three temperature regimes. Two were thermostatic at 50 °C and 65 °C with the third set of samples being alternated (thermally stepped) at weekly intervals between the two previously mentioned temperatures.

Dielectric measurements were conducted on a Hewlett Packard HP 8753A network analyser, connected to a computer, scanning the joints through the frequency range of 300 kHz to 3 GHz, Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic of the high frequency dielectric testing technique using the HP8753A network analyser.

Calibration of the network analyser was carried out using three standard connections that had known reflection coefficients over the frequency range 300 kHz to 3 GHz; a short circuit, an open circuit and a 50 Ω load.

To correlate and justify the measured changes in dielectric properties, destructive mechanical testing was conducted. This consisted of Mode I cleavage testing and Mode II shear analysis. As the former yields more information at this stage of testing, only the cleavage test data will be presented.

The modified cleavage test used was based on ASTM 3433-93 - fracture strength in cleavage of adhesives in bonded metal joints and ASTM 3807-93 - strength properties of adhesives in peel by tension loading. The test uses specimens of dimensions detailed in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Joint dimensions for aluminium cleavage test specimen.

A Zwick tensile testing machine was used to apply a crosshead separation rate of 3 mm/minute. White correction fluid applied to one edge of the joint allowed for crack propagation to be monitored. At 5 mm crack length intervals the load was recorded, up to 45 mm, then reduced to half its final load, before being reapplied to get a second crack initiation reading. This procedure generated a crack initiation value at the crack tip, as well as for the

bulk of the specimen (45 mm from crack tip) and load values for the adhesive between these two points.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At weekly intervals, 10 specimen joints from each temperature regime were dielectrically tested, along with control samples aged at 50 °C and 65 °C in dry ovens and one batch under ambient laboratory conditions. From the frequency domain measurements, dielectric loss and permittivity were plotted through the frequency range for all 60 samples. For each temperature set, one joint was selected and graphed with data from previous weeks. Considering these traces, the value for dielectric loss and permittivity at 3 MHz was extracted for each week, with the latter plotted in Figure 3, along with the other ageing temperature sets.

Figure 3: Change in dielectric permittivity at 3 MHz, due to ageing under controlled conditions, up to 248 days. Thermal step trace marked with 50's and 65's indicating temperature of step prior to testing.

◆ Wet 65 °C, + Wet thermally stepped, ▼ Wet 50 °C, ▲ Dry room temp, ■ Dry 50 °C, ● Dry 65 °C

It is evident from Figure 3 that the control samples were not changing, however ageing in water at elevated temperatures led to an increase in dielectric permittivity. This increase in permittivity was caused by and was directly related to moisture uptake within the adhesive. Also interesting is the trend of the thermally stepped sample. A gradient variation occurs each week, depending on the ageing temperature prior to testing. It should also be noticed that the thermally stepped trace tends towards the 50 °C aged sample rather than a mid-way position, despite being aged at 65 °C and 50 °C equally.

Time domain data was measured for each ageing temperature regime, along with the control specimens, and graphed in a similar manner to those in frequency domain. Figure 4 illustrates the time domain graphs for the sample aged in water at 65 °C for 248 days.

Figure 4: TDR trace of control specimen aged for 248 days at room temperature.

The largest negative peak (~0ns) is caused by the adhesive joint having a smaller characteristic impedance than the coaxial cable connection, resulting in a reflection from this interface. The traces then exhibit a series of positive pulses of diminishing amplitude, which are the reflections from the end of the joint where an adhesive/air interface exists. The decrease in amplitude of the pulse is related to the energy of the electrical signal being reduced as it travels up and down the specimen. What is also evident from Figure 4 is the excellent repeatability achieved using this technique and the very little change of properties under dry ageing conditions.

As illustrated in Figure 3, the dielectric permittivity increased as the joints were aged in water, the higher the temperature, the greater the increase. Therefore, from equation (2) it is expected that the pulse transit time will increase with ageing. Figure 5 illustrates this effect with the peak to peak delay increasing as the sample is aged at 65 °C in water.

Figure 5: TDR trace of water aged joint at 65 °C for 248 days.

As ageing proceeds and flaws occur at the adhesive/adherent interface, it is expected that the time domain trace will detail additional smaller pulses. At this early point in ageing, such effects are not yet obvious enough to be detected.

Destructive mechanical testing was performed on samples before ageing to gain reference data, and then at specified intervals on water aged specimens. Shear test results have shown a drop in strength as ageing proceeded, however the cleavage test results yield more detailed information.

As the 65 °C water aged samples experienced the greatest effect, these will be discussed. The reference samples fractured predominantly by cohesive failure, with the recorded load decreasing as the crack propagated, plotted in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Cleavage test reference values for load against crack opening.

◆ 2Al-BA-01.20 ■ 2Al-BA-02.20 ▲ 2Al-BA-07.11 × 2Al-BA-08.21 — AVERAGE

For the samples aged at 65 °C under water, four joints were tested for each batch, removed after 14, 100 and 238 days. Figure 7 shows the average for each batch, plotted with errors showing the range of the four joints.

Figure 7: Average mechanical cleavage test results for epoxy/aluminium joints aged in water at 65 °C as a function of crack length.
 ■ Reference (t=0), ◆ 14 Days, ▲ 100 Days, ▼ 238 Days.

After 14 days submerged at 65 °C, only a slight reduction in strength was measured and the failure remained cohesive. At 100 days and 238 days, the cleavage strength was further diminished, but with greater loss at the crack tip, where the water had been able to attack from the crack tip as well as the sides.

The modified cleavage test also allowed for visual analysis and Figure 8 illustrates one joint from each batch as time progressed. This clearly details that adhesive failure was occurring around the exposed edges, with the bulk of the adhesive maintaining cohesive failure. Therefore the measured loss in strength especially at the crack tip was a consequence of the change in failure mechanism from cohesive to adhesive. Further to this, in Figure 7, the maximum details the extent of adhesive failure into the joint from the crack tip.

Figure 8: Visual analysis of epoxy/aluminium joints after destructive cleavage testing having been aged under water for 0 (reference), 14, 100 and 238 days.

When the non-destructive dielectric results and the load values gained from destructive mechanical testing were analysed, a distinctive trend was observed. In Figure 9, the change in dielectric permittivity at 3 MHz has been plotted against the load at 25 mm, for epoxy/aluminium cleavage joints.

Figure 9: Correlation between dielectric permittivity at 3 MHz and cleavage load at 25 mm.
 ■ Wet 65 °C ● Wet 50 °C ▲ Wet Thermally Stepped

Evidently the two measurements are closely related, regardless of the temperature that the joints were aged under. Similarly, when the shear test results were considered, a matching graph was obtained, illustrating the potential for high frequency dielectrics as a non-destructive technique to evaluate the strength of adhesively bonded structures when exposed to water.

CONCLUSION

The studies on water aged joints at elevated temperatures have indicated detrimental effects which may be non-destructively evaluated. High frequency dielectric methods have been used to detect very slight changes in dielectric permittivity and loss, caused as a result of water ingress. Also illustrated has been the effect temperature has on this uptake, both thermostatic and thermally stepped. Most importantly, the non-destructive technique has easily detected moisture well before catastrophic failure of the adhesive joint. This was detailed by the slight losses in strength, found using the modified Mode I cleavage test.

As ageing progresses, more adhesive failure is anticipated, followed by interfacial flaws, further reducing the strength of the bond. It is expected that high frequency time domain analysis will be able to detect such a loss of structural integrity of the adhesive joint.

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